

THE WAYS OF IMPROVING VOCABULARY.

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Annotation: This article provides information about how to improve pupils vocabulary. Teaching English is very challenging nowadays. Senior high school students urgently are needed to be communicative in using English well. They need to be able to develop their English skills well. Dealing with mastering English skills, vocabulary is one of the crucial language components in learning English.

Key words: vocabulary, activities, reading habit

Vocabulary is one language component that plays an important role in mastering skills in English. Without having good and sufficient vocabulary, learners will be difficult in understanding and comprehending words when they listen, speak, read and write in English. Vocabulary mastery is one of the crucial things that learners have to master. Learners who have good and sufficient vocabulary mastery will be easy to communicate and comprehend information in English. As a result, they are able to read books, newspapers, journals, and the article in English easily. They can speak English fluently and even they can comprehend what they listen to. Automatically they can easily express their idea in writing activity. In other words, mastering vocabulary will help them to master English skills well. Teaching vocabulary is challenging for English teachers in Indonesia. There are many aspects of vocabulary teaching and learning which have been investigated and researched. In fact, problems still found. Students still have problems in learning and mastering vocabulary. As a result, they cannot comprehend texts in English well, they get stuck when they listen to the conversation in English and they speak English doubly. Those problems impact their communication skills in English.

An improved and expanded vocabulary will boost you on a personal and particularly professional level; the benefits are manifold. Explore the beauty and potential of a language. Communicate in a more engaging, entertaining way. Speak without confusion on any subject. Become a better writer or enhance your overall reading experience. The sky is the limit.

Assuming you have interest in the topic, we are on the same road trying to constantly add new expressions to our pool of active and passive words. In this comprehensive article I will therefore outline techniques to show you how to improve vocabulary on a daily basis. It ranges from setting goals and playing games to writing exercises and language learning. The vocabulary activities and tips are grouped by similarity but can be applied in no specific order. Most of us have not spent much time learning new vocabulary since we were high school or college students. Thankfully you can always pick up where you left off. Here are some tips to help you start learning new vocabulary words:

1. **Develop a reading habit.** Vocabulary building is easiest when you encounter words in context. Seeing words appear in a novel or a newspaper article can be far more helpful than seeing them appear on vocabulary lists. Not only do you gain exposure to unfamiliar words; you also see how they're used.
2. **Use the dictionary and thesaurus.** Online dictionaries and thesauruses are helpful resources if used properly. They can jog your memory about synonyms that would actually be better words in the context of what you're writing. A full dictionary definition can also educate you about antonyms, root words, and related words, which is another way to learn vocabulary.
3. **Play word games.** Classic games like Scrabble and Boggle can function as a fun way to expand your English vocabulary. Crossword puzzles can as well. If you really want to be efficient, follow up rounds of these word games with a little note-taking. Keep a list of the different words you learned while playing the game, and then study that list from time to time.

4. **Use flashcards.** A quick way to build a large vocabulary is to study a number of words via flashcards. In today's digital age, a wide array of smartphone apps make flashcards convenient and easy to organize. Aiming for one new word a day is reasonable. You can always go for more, but it may not be reasonable to assimilate dozens of English words every single day.
5. **Subscribe to “word of the day” feeds.** Some web platforms will provide you with a word a day—either on a website, an app, or via email—to help you expand your vocabulary. You can add these words to running word lists.
6. **Use mnemonics.** A mnemonic device is a form of word association that helps you remember words' definitions and proper uses. For instance think of the word *obsequious* which means “attempting to win favor from influential people by flattery.” Break down that word into components: “obse” is the beginning of “obsessed,” “qui” sounds like the French word for “yes” (*oui*), and “us” is like the word “us.” So you can think of that big word *obsequious* as “obsessed with saying yes to us”—which is kind of what it means!
7. **Practice using new words in conversation.** It's possible to amass a huge vocabulary without actually knowing how to use words. This means you have to take it upon yourself to put your personal dictionary into use. If you come across an interesting word in your reading, make a point of using it in conversation. By experimenting in low-stakes situations, you can practice the art of word choice and, with a little bit of trial and error, hone in on the right word for a particular context.

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